

High Directivity and Gain Enhancement for Small Planar Dipole Antenna at 11 GHz Using Symmetrical Pyramidal Block Base on Epsilon Negative Medium

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Abstract : This paper aims to improve high directivity and high gain of Small Planar Dipole Antenna (SPDA) by using Symmetrical Pyramidal Block (SPB) which operates in X band at 11 GHz. The SPB is designed by using metamaterials concept with Epsilon Negative Medium (ENG) and Epsilon Near-Zero (ENZ) ($|\epsilon| < 1$). The results of the simulation show that the SPB is able to enhance directivity and gain for the SPDA by maximum gain at 2.46 in theta and phi direction. The return loss is -13.7037 dB with narrow beam width. These results were simulated by the High Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS).

Keywords : Small Planar Dipole Antenna, Symmetrical Pyramidal Block, metamaterials, Epsilon Near-Zero, Epsilon Negative Medium

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